

FOREIGN TRAVELS BY GOVERNMENT OFFICIALS AND ESTACODE: IMPLICATIONS ON PUBLIC FINANCES IN NIGERIA: 2015 - 2023

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the implications of foreign travels by government officials and estacode on public finances in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023. The pineapple theory of equitable, but shrewd distribution of government resources as espoused by Udoh was adopted, while qualitative survey research design with basically secondary method of data collection, such as books, journals, newspapers, conference papers, government publications and the internet were used for the enquiry. The ex-post facto research design and content analysis were adopted as methods of data analysis. Two subsidiary objectives were set, including determining whether the nature of government financial regulations was the major reason why government officials mostly benefitted from regular foreign travels and estacode in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023. The research questions also included knowing whether the nature of government financial regulations was the major reason why government officials mostly benefitted from regular foreign travels and estacode in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023. The two null (H_0) hypotheses, included that the nature of government financial regulations tended not to be the major reason why government officials mostly benefitted from regular foreign travels and estacode in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023; Whereas, the first of the two findings showed that, the nature of government financial regulations was the major reason why government officials mostly benefitted from regular foreign travels and estacode in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023. Based on the findings, it was first recommended that the federal government review government financial regulations to stem the tide of foreign travel by government officials and check the excessive spending on estacode by reducing the number of foreign trips and officials on a given trip.

KEYWORDS: Foreign travels, government officials, estacode and public finances.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign travels are trips embarked upon in countries outside a person's country. As good and interesting as foreign travels could be, they have over time become a means of depleting or syphoning public funds to both individual pockets or as capital flight to foreign countries. In Nigeria, both governments and private sector have over the years embraced foreign travels as veritable means for international conferences, meetings and seminars. Others have also embarked on foreign travels for holidays, medical and other forms of tourism. Due to the poor conditions of health facilities in Nigeria, many wealthy Nigerians both in public and private sectors have taken advantage of foreign travels to meet their health needs in countries like: India, Britain, London and in the UK. Another very critical factor that has made foreign travels not only interesting, but also money making ventures is the estacode that is paid to every government official or private sector operative who embarks on any official trips abroad.

Estacode is a term used in government, especially in the context of international travel allowances. It refers to the daily allowance or stipend provided to public officials who are travelling outside their usual work location, typically to another city or country. Nigeria's political, public and judicial office holders get a combined sum of \$24,385 as estacode for every night they spend when travelling, data from the Revenue Mobilization, Allocation and Fiscal Commission (RMAFC, 2021) has shown. The Chief Justice of Nigeria gets the highest pay with \$2,000 per night, followed by the Justice of the Supreme Court, Appeal Court President and Senate President having \$1,300 each, the data revealed. RMAFC had said public office holders often abused the remuneration package, leading to the commission being criticized for fixing high amounts for allowances. "Perhaps, the most challenging issue the Commission faces is the abuse by stakeholders at both the National, States and Local Government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package for political, public and judicial office holders," the commission said. "This has left the general public with the impression that the Commission fixed jumbo pay for political, public and judicial office holders in spite of several clarifications by the Commission in the media on the matter, Keyamo (2015). Due to some diseases, including COVID-19 that had posed some constraints on foreign travels some time ago, Udoh *et al* (2022) had traced "the origin of COVID 19 outbreak" to have "been linked to a Human Seafood market in China that deals with the sale of live animals..."

On a final note, an abridged overview of public finance by Atkinson *et al* (1980) holds that public finance is the study of the role of the government in the economy. It is the branch of economics that assesses the government revenue and of the public authorities and the adjustment of one or the other to achieve desirable effects and avoid undesirable ones (Udoh, 2018). But, Buchanan (1987) in Udoh (2018) has provided the purview of public finance as being considered to be threefold, consisting of governmental effects on: the efficient allocation of available resources; the distribution among citizens; and the of the economy. It is however, based on the foregoing that this research is set to investigate the implications of foreign travels by government officials and estacode on public finances in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Foreign travels are supposed to be trips embarked upon in countries outside a person's country. But as good and interesting as foreign travels could be, they have over time become a means of depleting or syphoning public funds to both individual pockets or as capital flights to foreign countries. In Nigeria, both governments and private sector have over the years embraced foreign travels as veritable means for international conferences, meetings, seminars and so on. Others have also embarked on foreign travels for holidays, medical and other forms of tourism. Also, due to the poor conditions of health facilities in Nigeria, many wealthy Nigerians both in public and private sectors have taken advantage of foreign travels to meet their health needs in countries like: India, Britain, London and in the UK. Another very critical factor that has made foreign travels not only interesting, but also money making ventures is the estacode that is paid to every government official or private sector operative who embarks on any official trips abroad, which is basically the essence of carrying out this research in order to find out the reason(s) why government officials seem to mostly benefit from this aspect of provisions to its workers.

It is unfortunate to state that in Nigeria, once an avenue of making money from government is created or discovered, a larger majority of the people will want to exploit it. Udoh *et al* (2019) has considered the level of exploitation meted on the Nigeria's economy by stakeholders as "a serious issue of great concern". This may be the idea behind the assertion by Odum (2003) in Udoh *et al* (2017) as saying that "Today, the language of money (not ideas) and acts that are symptomatic of interminable ideological heterogeneity has become part of the ... political shibboleth". And, as already noted in the background to the study, estacode has become a very juicy means of making money by government officials in Nigeria to the extent that it has become very worrisome to both academics and journalists as well. This negates Ime T. Akpan's idea of public financial management while writing Nwaeze (2009) foreword as quoted in Udoh *et al* (2018) as saying that its topical and sensitive objectives "are to ensure that public funds are frugally managed according to laid down principles"

Due to the rate at which foreign travels are embraced by Nigerians and the desire to push further, it became evidently clear that government has not done enough to forestall incessant foreign travels in future and excessive spending of government finances through estacode. Having stated the obvious, it seems that apart from the estacode received by intending travelers, most Nigerians have personal interests attached to their envisioned foreign trips. This has therefore created much pressure on the scheme and has weighed great financial burden on the finances of government. It is on this note that this research is set to investigate foreign travels of government officials and estacode as means of depleting public finances in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023. The main objective of this research was to investigate the implications of foreign travels by government officials and estacode on public finances in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following are the hypotheses of the study:

- a. The nature of government financial regulations tends not to be more likely the major reason why government officials mostly benefitted from regular foreign travels and estacode in

Nigeria between 2015 and 2023.

b. The cost of expenditure incurred by government officials on estacode during the period under review tends not to be very high.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Foreign travels:

For want of space, but before delving fully into the concept of public finance, it is imperative to briefly consider foreign travels as it precedes other variables on the topic of the research. Foreign travels are trips embarked upon in countries outside a person's country. Foreign travels can be both official and private in nature. But, the concern of this study is on the official (public) foreign travels which usually attract government sponsorship through the use of the tax-payers' money.

Public finance:

Atkinson, *et al* (1980) assert that public finance is the study of the role of the government in the economy. But, according to Blinder *et al* (1974) and Udoh (2024), public finance is the branch of economics that assesses the government revenue and government expenditure of the public authorities and the adjustment of one or the other to achieve desirable effects and avoid undesirable ones. In his original and edited works on public finance, Buchanan ([1967] 1987) provides the purview of public finance and considered it to be threefold, consisting of governmental effects on: the efficient allocation of available resources; the distribution of income among citizens; and the stability of the economy. And finally, Musgrave (2008) asked a pertinent question, why do governments choose to intervene in the way that they do? This question is centrally concerned with the study of political economy, theorizing how governments make public policy.

Financial regulation:

Financial regulation refers to the rules and laws firms operating in the financial industry, such as banks, credit unions, insurance companies, financial brokers and asset managers must follow. However financial regulation is more than just having rules in place - it's also about the ongoing oversight and enforcement of these rules. The Central Bank of Ireland regulates and supervises over 10,000 financial service providers operating in Ireland. Since 2014, the responsibility for supervising banks is shared between the Central Bank of Ireland and the European Central Bank (ECB). According to Benjamin (2015), financial regulation is a broad set of policies that apply to the financial sector in most jurisdictions, justified by two main features of finance: systemic risk, which implies that the failure of financial firms involves public interest considerations; and information asymmetry, which justifies curbs on freedom of contract in selected areas of financial services, particularly those that involve retail clients and/or Principal agent problems. An integral part of financial regulation is the supervision of designated financial firms and markets by specialized authorities such as securities commissions and bank supervisors.

Estacode:

Estacode is a term used in government, especially in the context of international travel allowances. It refers to the daily allowance or stipend provided to public officials who are travelling outside their usual work location, typically to another city or country. But, in Nigeria, "Estacode" refers to a form of travel allowance given to government officials. As usual we've

left out the entire meaning of the word in making up an acronym. Next time you hear this word remember it is purely a Nigerian lingua liken to broken English Udoh, (2024:1&2).

Here are what Nigerian ministers, senators and others get as estacode per night for foreign trips:

Estacode per night for Nigerian government officials

S/No.	Designation	Amount in Dollar (\$)
1	Minister	\$900
2	Minister of State	\$900
3	Special Adviser	\$800
4	Director General of MDA	\$900
5	Chief Justice of Nigeria	\$2,000
6	Justices of Supreme Court	\$1,300
7	Appeal Court President	\$1,300
8	Judges of Courts	\$1,100 / \$600
9	Senate President	\$1,300
10	Dep Senate President	\$1,100
11	Senators	\$950
12	House of Rep Speaker	\$1,200
13	Deputy H of R Speaker	\$1,000
14	House of Rep Members	\$900
15	Commissioners	\$600
16	Special Advisers (State)	\$500
17	DG/Perm Secs (State)	\$500
18	House Assembly Speaker	\$700
19	Dep House Speaker	\$650
20	House Members (State)	\$600
21	LGA Chairman/Vice	\$450
22	Supervisory Councilors	\$400
23	LGA Special Advisers	\$400
24	LGA Legislative Leaders	\$225
25	Dep LGA Leg. Leaders	\$220
26	Councilors of LGA	\$210

Source: Keyamo (2015), NCAA pivotal to Nigeria's 71% score in aviation security audit - Achimugu

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK:

a. Pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories

The study makes use of pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories (Udoh, 2024) as propounded by Dr. Unwana- Abasi S. Udoh, Lecturer in the Department of Public Administration, Akwa Ibom State University in 2023. The pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories are theories for the distribution of government resources. The theories offer the managers of government resources two vital contemplations and scenarios in the sharing of government resources or public goods. They are postulated using basic natural resources, such as pawpaw/papaya and pineapple fruits. Pawpaw or papaya (botanical name) as well as pineapple fruits are agricultural products and are considered most appropriate when they are fully ripped for use in demonstrating the sharing processes. These thoughts, which are supported by Basic Resources Theory (Udoh, 2017), are advanced in attempt to resolve the surrounding issues on the concepts of equality and equity in the sharing of national and state resources in Nigeria, in particular and in the globe, in general.

While the pawpaw/papaya theory has a single sharing stream, the pineapple formula has two variances, the vertical and the horizontal perspectives. The case in point is that, with fiscal federalism in mind, which places premium on how financial resources of government are shared among the federal, states and local government areas, the pawpaw/papaya theory represents equality, fairness and justice on the one hand; while pineapple theory represents equity and shrewdness on the other, respectively. In Udoh *et al*, (2018) the idea of fiscal federalism has received the endorsement of John Rawls' theory of justice whose basic assumption bothers on "the socially just distribution of goods in a society."

A cursory and critical observation reveals that adopting the pineapple theory in financial sharing, among tiers of government is to attempt some level of subtlety and shrewdness towards the lower levels of government by the higher level of government. This is so due to the assumption that, pineapple does not ripe round the entire fruit equally, at the same time, unlike pawpaw/papaya. This implies that without any careful observation on the use of pawpaw/papaya approach in the financial sharing among tiers of government, the system or the process offers total fairness, equality and justice among all levels of government. The reason is also based on the assumption that, pawpaw rips round the entire body equally, at the same time, unlike pineapples that any consumer who picks any part of the fruit must enjoy total sweetness. The author therefore, assures that the proper use of pawpaw theory is an antidote for a peaceful and harmonious co-existent of all the component parts of a nation or state, even though it may generate bad blood among the richer components whose greater goods may serve the greater happiness of the less-richer components. Whereas, the author warns that the use of pineapple theory can create room for further acrimonies and agitations on the authorities for more attention by the component parts of a nation or state, except the horizontal variance of the pineapple theory is adopted, instead of the vertical stream. These theories are authenticated by Udoh, U.S. (2014), Udoh, U.S. (2017), Udoh, U.S. *et al* (2017), Mboho, K.S. *et al* (2018) and Udoh, U.S. *et al* (2018).

b. Pineapple Theory:

Application of the pineapple theory to the study:

Udoh (2024) further propounded the Pineapple Approach as representing **equity and shrewdness**. From the table below, showing **Estacode per night for Nigerian government officials, there is no element of equality, but equity in all the distribution process there.**

This therefore, implies that pineapple theory represents equity and shrewdness rather than equality. However, the major assumption of pawpaw/papaya theory is that if pineapple is peeled and sliced into smaller, but equal parts and into a bowl, it is argued that because pineapple does not ripe round the entire fruits equally, at the same time, a consumer must pick a part of the head of the fruit in order to enjoy the total sweetness that the fruit contains. Otherwise, picking the tail of the fruit will leave the consumer with a soared tongue, instead of sweetness. Based on this premise, the author argues that if financial operators adopt pineapple theory as a guiding principle or as their sharing formula in allocating the nation's or state's financial resources to government officials for foreign travels, that the action is equity and shrewdness.

In this theory, it is only the fruitier that knows exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail, and what part of the bowl were the different parts shuffled. The fact in point is that, not all parts of pineapple fruit give equal and satisfying taste of sweetness to the consumers. Therefore, rom the above assumption, there are two streams to the explanation of the pineapple theory. One is the vertical and two is the horizontal sharing formulae. In the vertical sharing formula, the fruitier of the resources first of all, divides the pineapple vertically into two equal parts, from head to tail before chopping the fruit into consumable sizes. The consumable pieces are placed and shuffled in a bowl before consumers are made to partake in eating the fruit. This implies that, despite the official sharing parameters of the resources, government resources can also, first of all be shared equally, before it is shared equitably. The equitable distribution of public goods or funds is imbedded with subtle shrewdness and can create room for further acrimonies and agitations on the authorities for more attention by those who don't have a fair share of the resources.

But, in the horizontal sharing formula, the fruitier of resources divides the pineapple horizontally into two parts, before chopping each part of the fruit into consumable sizes. The consumable pieces are placed in two separate bowls and shuffled before consumers are made to partake in eating the fruit, first from the bowl where the tail of the fruit were shuffled, before eating the fruit in the second bowl that the head of the fruit was sliced into. In the horizontal sharing formula, the consumers have equal chance to have a feel of the different tests in the two different bowls.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the qualitative survey research design because the study involves longitudinal investigations. ABS (2021) in Udoh *et al* (2024) stated that, "A longitudinal survey study involves examining survey responses over a certain timeframe to investigate whether there is any change in your variables of interest. In such a design, your survey needs to be administered at least twice – once at the start and at the end of the timeframe. You may also opt to administer it in the middle of the timeframe as well. As such, both primary and secondary methods of enquiry were made use of. The primary data were basically from personal observations and interviews, while the secondary data were drawn from relevant text books, journals, newspapers and the internet.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the researcher posited that the nature of government financial regulations is the major reason why government officials mostly benefitted from regular

foreign travels and estacode in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023, while the cost of expenditure incurred by government officials on estacode during the period under review are rather very high. Based on the two hypotheses in this study, two findings were also made and are summarized as follows: that the nature of government financial regulations is the major reason why government officials mostly benefitted from regular foreign travels and estacode in Nigeria between 2015 and 2023; and, that the cost of expenditure incurred by government officials on estacode during the period under review are rather very high and as such some useful recommendations were made to checkmate the trend.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. That the federal government should review government financial regulations in order to stem the tide of foreign travels by government officials and checkmate the excessive spending on estacode by reducing the number of foreign trips as well as the number of officials on a given trip.
- ii. That the federal government should facilitate similar trainings in Nigeria as obtainable overseas, in order to save the costs accruable from estacode, since overseas training opportunities were not the only major motivation for government officials to regularly embark on foreign travels within the period under investigation, but that personal interests were attached to them.

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